

Title: Community Trust and Wellbeing in Displacement Settings: Lessons from Kyangwali, Uganda.

Background:

Misinformation in displacement settings erodes trust and negatively affects the psychosocial wellbeing of the Red Cross and Red Crescent volunteers and staff. This makes it a barrier in humanitarian interventions for the frontline responders. Harmful myths and false rumours about humanitarian health interventions, especially blood donation, have been found to affect confidence of frontline responders during humanitarian crises, which constrains service delivery and impacts on their safety in such displacement settings.

Methodology:

This 2-month study from October – December 2025 established a community led initiative by forming local trust networks to detect and address misinformation among targeted 500 community members. A mixed methods design approach was employed, using purposive sampling to recruit study participants. These included structured interviews, focus group discussions, and key informant interviews. The intervention was supported by multilingual communication tools and volunteers of the Uganda Red Cross from diverse ethnicities. The idea of Information Hygiene, a strategy for detecting and immediately eliminating harmful myths and misconceptions served as the intervention's compass.

Findings:

Pre and post survey intervention assessments indicate a decrease in misinformation and enhanced understanding of important health information in the targeted 500 community members. 6 in 10 people had accurate knowledge on the importance of humanitarian health interventions like blood donation compared to the initial 2 in 10. This improved the psychosocial wellbeing for frontline responders by strengthening trust between them and Kyangwali community members.

Significance:

The study findings indicate that local trust networks and an Information Hygiene approach counter misinformation surrounding humanitarian health interventions. These strategies offer a scalable and adaptable model for strengthening trust and protecting frontline responders in similar settings hence improving their psychosocial wellbeing and the overall community health. Embedding such strategies increases participation rates in humanitarian health interventions.

Key words: Humanitarian Response, Misinformation, Psychosocial wellbeing, Health Interventions.